

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. A 462

DATE: 26 16 196

Take off : 09 28 41
Landing : 15 33 23

Aircraft Scientist	: A KAYE / H RICHER	Captain	: C O'BRIEN
Flight Leader	: O BRIGGS	Co-pilot	: M PURSE
Others	: M PICKERING	Navigator	: J AIKES
	J PANTRY	Engineer	: K QUICK
		Loadmaster	: J CANNING
	I RYLE / J CRAWFORD		
	K DEWEY / S KENT / S KESSLER		
	S OS BOENE		
	M RYLE		
	S WILSON		
	W DAVIES		

Trials Instructions :
Operating area :

General synoptic situation

TIME :

A462 26-JUN-96 11:07:00-13:59:00GMT

A462 26-JUN-96 Height time series

A456, 8th May 1996

<u>TIME (EM)</u>		<u>HEIGHT</u>	<u>HDG</u>
092841	Take off from Boscombe Down		
100407(13)-103831(14)	Run 1	FL240	300°
104047(15)-110516(16)	Run 2	FL240	260°
110728(17)-113630(21)	Profile P1	FL240 - 50'	190°/000°
113804(22)-114305(23)	Run 3.1	100'	090°
114502(24)-115321(25)	Run 3.2	100'	270°
115516(26)-120216(27)	Run 3.3	100'	090°
120414(28)-120917(29)	Run 4.1	2600'	270°
121135(30)-121636(31)	Run 4.2	2600'	090°
121845(32)-122346(34)	Run 4.3	2600'	250°
122530(35)-123054(36)	Run 5.1	3000'	090°
123220(37)-123737(38)	Run 5.2	3000'	270°
123859(39)-124402(40)	Run 5.3	3000'	090°
124553(41)-125044(42)	Run 6.1	3500'	270°
125207(43)-125733(44)	Run 6.2	3500'	090°
125858(45)-130401(46)	Run 6.3	3500'	270°
130837(47)-131417(49)	Run 7.1	2300'	100°
131535(50)-132053(51)	Run 7.2	1900'	270°
132223(52)-132804(53)	Run 7.3	1900'	090°
134024(55)-134524(56)	Run 8.1	2000'	090°
134456(57)-135200(58)	Run 8.2	2000'	270°
135320(59)-135820(60)	Run 8.3	2000'	090°

ENGINE FAULT - SORTIE ABORTED

155323 Land at Boscombe Down

Sortie Brief:

VACC - ACSOE/MAGE

Colin O'Dowd

Objective: To examine cloud-induced aerosol growth in the marine boundary layer during a phytoplankton plume and the evolution of DMS and Hydrocarbons in the marine boundary layer

Location: Up-wind and West of Mace Head, off the Irish Coast

Meteorological Conditions: Maritime air mass, non-broken stratocumulus cloud deck
Tropical or mid-Atlantic air mass back trajectory

- Flight Pattern:**
- (1) Profile from transit altitude to 50 ft into initial start point - P1
Start point is to be approximately 120-140 km upwind of ship location 53°30' N, 11° 30' W.
 - (2) Conduct k-gamma run; R1.1; R1.2
 - (3) perform stack comprising 3x5 min reciprocal VACC runs at each level. DMS and HC flask samples are highlighted when required.
R 2.1-3 30m amsl (DMS & HC)
R3.1-3 50m below cloud base (DMS)
R4.1-3 30-50m above cloud base (DMS & HC)
R5.1-3 50m above cloud top (DMS & HC)
 - (4) Transit to 40km downwind; Perform VACC run 50m below cloud base: R6.1-3 (DMS)
 - (5) Transit another 40 km downwind; perform VACC run 50m below cloud: R7.1-3 (DMS); In vicinity of ship RRS Challenger 53°30' N, 11° 30' W.
 - (6) Transit another 40 km downwind; perform VACC run 50m below cloud base: R8.1-3 (DMS & HC); and 30-50m above cloud base: R9.1-3 (DMS)
 - (7) Profile to surface and conduct full profile from 50ft to transit level home.

Note: VACC tubes to be used Tube 1 (ambient 30°C - this may need resetting); Tube 3 (150°C); and Tube 4 (300°C). Both DMS and HC flasks require 5 minutes fill time. If both samples are required on same VACC run these can be taken on first and third reciprocal legs.

Ship Information: to follow later from Wendy Broadgate

Mace Head Sounding time 15:00-17:00 (local time) providing no cloud present over Mace Head.

WEDNESDAY 26 JUNE 1996

FLIGHT A462 VACC

Weather: High pressure to west of Ireland. bank
of SC. To ~~the~~ SW of Ireland.

Debrief: The Sortie was cut short due to a pitch lock
on propellor No 2. Most of the essential science
had be completed under a slightly broken SC
deck. With the exception of re locating
to ~~the~~ 53N 12W the sortie brief was ~~followed~~
followed almost exactly until the IFE.

All scientific kit performed well.

Andrew Kaye

NERC AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST.

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: A.

Project: VACC

Date: 24/6/16

Flight No: A462

Page 1 of 6

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
						09:40:59	/		
09:45:59	/	/	17.9	P	328	51.55	-5.04	Hazy no sky visible or ground below	
09:54:09	/	/	22.0	P	293	51.79	-3.70	Sc below haze lay at current alt. <small>parnis</small>	
09:58								engine peak in haze layer dropped as we climbed out.	
09 10:00:15	/	/	24000	P				reached cruise alt. Sc below. clear above <small>some ci ahead.</small>	
10:04:07	R1	R1	F240	P	290	51.95	-4.78	Sc below clear above ci ahead.	
10:21:34		R1	F240	P	290			7/8 Sc below Ci above. clear below to south.	
10:26:46		R1	F240	P	287	52.46	-7.39	7/8 Sc below Steaky Ci above some breaks in ci ahead.	
10:38:40		R1	F240	P	286	52.69	-8.82	6/8 cu below ci above clear ahead to south of <small>note pit</small> area	
10:40:47		R2	F240	P	252	52.66	-9.14	4/8 Sc below — patchy ci above.	
10:46:31		R2	F240	P	252	52.51	-9.75	Sc sheet breaking up over coast. ci above.	
10:51:20		R2	F240	P	252	52.37	-10.30	clear below and above some cloud to south over land.	

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: A. Kunge H. Richer.

Project: ~~A462~~ ^{VACC} Date: 26/6/96
 Flight No: A 462 Page 2 of 6

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
11:04:10	15	R2	FL 270		261	52.02	-11.78	thin ci above the small in fields below.	
11:05:16	16	R2e	Lto	FL	261				
11:07:27	17	P1	240	FL	182	52.91	-12.06	ci above clear below with small in fields visible.	
11:11:10								large 20,200	
11:15:50		P1	14700	FL	185			Co & aerosol peak small in below Si above.	
11:19:29		P1	11200	FL	184	51.08	-12.00	Sc ahead broken on below Ci ahead.	
11:23:05		P1	8200	P		50.89	-12.00	bottom of aerosol level. air drying out on T@phi	
11:25:58		P1	5000	P	183	50.71	-12.00	Sc below some ci above.	
								3300 cloud top. 2800 cloud base gaps - 2700 700 feet thick	
11:33:18	19	P1 int	1200	P	183	50.32	-12.03	thin sc above.	
11:34:13	20	P1	1200	P	183 352	50.34	-12.01		

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: A. Kyrre H. Richer.

Project: VACC Date: 26/6/96
Flight No: A462 Page 3 of 6

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
11:36:35	21	R1 end	50ft	R	1354	50.45 -12.06	1029 sea state 2 thin sc. above.		
11:38:04	22	R3.1	100ft	R	84	50.49 -11.97	thin sc. above.		
11:43:05	23	R3.1	100ft	R	.		smat from under SC sheet. extend second Run to compensate.		
11:45:02	24	3.2	100ft	R	266	50.53 -11.61	back under sc sheet.		
11:53:20	25	3.2e	100ft	R		50.59 -12.22	end of run moving south to clear edge.		
11:54:26	26	3.3	100ft	R	78.	50.37 -12.14.	sc above.		
11:57:57							Hannah taking over for a while		
							Run extended 2 minutes and 17:02:16 end of run		
12:04:15	27	R4.1	2.2 ft	P		50.35 -11.38	SC above - JUST IN LOWEST EDGE NOT VERY THICK (SOME CLEAR PATCHES)		
12:04:17		R4.1 end	2600 ft				END CLOUD COVER 8/8ths; WATER COLOUR NOTED TO BE DIFFERENT - GREEN		
12:11:35	28	R4.2	2600 ft			50.37 -12.01	SC 7/8ths NOT THICK NO BATTERIES FOR VIDEO CAMERA - PUT ON TO CHARGE		
12:16:36		R4.2 end					IN CLOUD FOR A LITTLE WHILE		

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Project: VACC Date: 20/6/96

Aircraft Scientist: A. KAYE H. RICHOR Flight No: A462 Page 4 of 6

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
12:17:18						50.26	-11.36	APPEAR TO COME OUT OF CLOUD	
12:18:45	29	R4.3	2600ft			50.42	-11.66	GOING BACK UNDER THIN CLOUD SOME BREAKS 7/8ths.	
12:23:46		R4.3 END						PROFILE UP TO 2900ft ENTERING CLOUD - RATHER THIN	
12:25:30	30	R5.1	3000ft			50.26	-11.96	FSSP SHOWING IN CLOUD 7μ effective radius	
12:30:54		R5.1 END				50.30	-11.48	SOME BLUE SKY NOTED BUT NOT MORE THAN 1/8th clear LOW O ₃ 27 ppb LOW CO 7/8	
12:32:20	31	R5.2	3000ft 2950			50.27	-11.53	CLOUD NOT BROKEN (CLOUD BURNING OFF FROM NORTH)	
12:37:37		R5.2 END				50.23	-11.97	PULLING OUT OF CLOUD ON TURN	
12:38:59	32	R5.3	3000ft			50.21	-11.9	BACK INTO CLOUD AT START OF RUN 12:40:20 OUT OF CLOUD FOR 15s	
12:44:02		R5.3 END						CO & O ₃ still low & steady UP TO 3500 ft ABOVE CLOUD THIN CIRRUS	
12:45:43	33	R6.1	3500ft					THIN CIRRUS ABOVE, HAZE AHEAD NOTABLE CO ₂ INCREASE 35 ppb, AEROSOL	
12:50:44		R6.1 END						TURNING	
12:52:07	34	R6.2	3500ft			50.12	-11.95	AGAIN HAZY, CIRRUS ABOVE CALM WIND (1 knot 002/1)	

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Project: VACC Date: 26/6/96

Aircraft Scientist: AKAYE H RICHER Flight No: A462 Page 5 of 6

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
12:57:33		R6.2						SOME MEDIUM LEVEL CLOUD NOTED, RATHER HAZY O ₃ CONTINUES TO BE ~ 40 ppb	
12:58:58	35	R6.3	3500ft					THIN HIGH CIRROS 1/8 HAZY 13:02:54 CLOUD (BASE) IS RATHER THIN	
13:04:01		R6.3 END				50.06		SOME GAPS IN CLOUD NOTED TO END OF RUN	
						-11.92		PROGRESS SOUTH EASTERLY (~20 MILES)	
13:08:37	36	R7.1	2300ft			49.91		(4) BELOW LAST WISPS OF CLOUD.	
						-11.65		WIND 375/1 O ₃ BACK TO BOUNDARY	
13:11:06								LAYER LEVEL 26 ppb, CO no change	
								HOLES IN CLOUD ABOVE BUT NOT	
13:12:40								FOR MORE THAN 20 SECONDS	
								INTO CLOUD 13:12:40 DESCENDING (1900ft)	
13:14:17		R7.1 END						A LITTLE TO GET OUT OF CLOUD	
13:15:35	37	R7.2	1900ft			49.81		ON VERY EDGE OF CLOUD (LOWER EDGE)	
						-11.67		BUT BELOW MAIN BASE HAZY	
13:20:51		R7.2 END				49.81			
						-11.67			
13:22:23	38	R7.3	1900ft			49.77		HAZY, NO FSSP / FEW FSSP COUNTS	
						-11.62		REPORTS 8/8 STRATOCUMULOS ABOVE	
13:28:05		R7.3 END				49.76		REPOSITION FOR PATTERN PART (5)	
						-11.10			
13:31:03								CLEAR SKY ABOVE (HOLE IN SC)	
								WIND 339/6	

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Project: VACC Date: 26/6/96

Aircraft Scientist: A KAYE M RICHOR Flight No: A462 Page 6 of 6

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
	8	8						RUN AVOIDING HOLE IN CLOUD! HOLES APPEARING IN CLOUD ^{WEST} GO SOUTH	
								PROFILE THROUGH CLOUD TO DETERMINE CLOUD THICKNESS AND BEST POSITION FOR RUN 8 ITEM (5)	
13:40:24		8.1	1900ft			49.35	-11.44		
13:45:3X	56	8.1e	1900			49.40	-11.03	Some big holes in Sc. at end of las	
13:46:57	57	8.2	2000			49.43	-11.10	heading back under cloud.	
13:52:02	58	8.2	2000		263	49.37	-11.50	hazy 7/8 Sc above. Sc	
13:53:19	59	8.3	2000			49.35	-11.41	Gap in cloud <u>above</u>	
13:58:23	60	8.3c	2000 P		80	49.46	-11.05	end of run out from under cloud engine #2 pitch lock... <u>problems</u>	
								engine will need to be shut down before landing.	
								<u>end of science</u>	

Flight Leader's In-Flight Log

Flight No A A462.....

Date 26/6/96.....

Page 1..... of 3.....

Video Tape	
No. <u>A462 #1</u>	
Ends <u>130</u>	
(FFC) / DFC / RFC	

	GPS	INU
Lat	<u>5104.86</u>	<u>5109.26</u>
Long	<u>1044.65</u>	<u>1044.68</u>
Time	<u>0839</u>	<u>0839.</u>
Status		

DRS recording to HORACE	☒ y / n
HORACE recording to disc	☒ y / n
SATCOM sending pos. reports	☒ y / n

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/ Sea st.
<u>090900</u>				<u>DATA</u>				<u>ON</u>	
<u>092044</u>				<u>TAKE OFF</u>					<u>RESCUE DOWN</u>
<u>100407</u>	<u>13</u>			<u>START RUN 1</u>					
		<u>FL240</u>		<u>300</u>	<u>200</u>	<u>-25.5</u>	<u>-34</u>	<u>OFF</u>	
				<u>END RUN 1</u>					
<u>103831</u>	<u>14</u>	<u>FL240</u>		<u>300</u>	<u>200</u>	<u>-25.5</u>	<u>-29.5</u>	<u>OFF</u>	
				<u>START RUN 2</u>					
<u>104047</u>	<u>15</u>	<u>FL240</u>		<u>260</u>	<u>200</u>	<u>-25.3</u>	<u>-30.1</u>	<u>OFF</u>	
				<u>END RUN 2</u>					
<u>110516</u>	<u>16</u>	<u>FL240</u>		<u>260</u>	<u>200</u>	<u>-24.2</u>	<u>-32.0</u>	<u>OFF</u>	
				<u>START PROFILE P1</u>					<u>1000 ft/min</u>
<u>110728</u>	<u>17</u>	<u>FL240</u>		<u>140</u>	<u>150</u>	<u>-23.8</u>	<u>-28.8</u>	<u>OFF</u>	
				<u>RECONF.</u>					
<u>112557</u>	<u>18</u>	<u>5000'</u>		<u>140</u>	<u>140</u>	<u>7.7</u>	<u>-42.500</u>		<u>ft/min</u>
				<u>END AT PROFILE P1</u>					
<u>113320</u>	<u>19</u>	<u>6000'</u>		<u>140</u>				<u>OFF</u>	
				<u>RECONF P1</u>					
<u>113418</u>	<u>20</u>	<u>12000'</u>		<u>000</u>	<u>100</u>				

Video Tape	
No.	4462 #1
Ends	1230
☒ FFC / ☐ DFC / ☐ RFC	

	GPS	INU
Lat		
Long		
Time		
Status		

DRS recording to HORACE	☒ y / ☐ n
HORACE recording to disc	☒ y / ☐ n
SATCOM sending pos reports	☒ y / ☐ n

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/ Sea st.
			END		PI				
113630	21	90'(60)	1024	0	180	13-2	6-8	OFF	Sea st. 2
			RUN	3.1					
113804	22	100'		90	180	13-2	6-5	OFF	
			END RUN	3.1					
114305	23	100'		90	180	13-2	7-2	OFF	
			START RUN	3-2					
114502	24	100'		270	180	13-1	7-3	OFF	Sea st. 3
			END RUN	3-2					
115321	25	100'		250	180	13-1	6-7	OFF	
			START RUN	3-3					
115516	26	100'		090	180	13-1	7-0	OFF	
			END RUN	3-3					
22 120216		100'		090	180	13-1	7-2	OFF	
			START RUN	4-1					
120444	28	2600'		270	180	5-9	5-4	OFF	
			END RUN	4-1					
120917	29	2600							
			START RUN	4-2					
121135	30	2600							
			END RUN	4-2					
121636	31	2600							

Flight Leader's In-Flight Log

Flight No A 462.....

Date 26/06/96.....

Page 2 of 3.....

Video Tape
No. <u>462 #1</u>
Ends: <u>1248?</u>
<u>FFC</u> / DFC / RFC

	GPS	INU
Lat		
Long		
Time		
Status		

DRS recording to HORACE ☒ y/n
HORACE recording to disc ☒ y/n
SATCOM sending pos. reports ☒ y/n

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/ Sea st.
				STAR R 4-3					
<u>12245</u>	<u>32</u>	<u>2600</u>		<u>270</u>	<u>185</u>	<u>61</u>	<u>5-7</u>	<u>OFF</u>	
				END RUN 4-3					
<u>12256</u>	<u>34</u>	<u>2600</u>							
				START RUN 5-1					
<u>122530</u>	<u>35</u>	<u>3000</u>		<u>90</u>	<u>180</u>	<u>46</u>	<u>5-4</u>	<u>OFF</u>	
				END RUN 5-1					
<u>123054</u>	<u>36</u>	<u>3000</u>		<u>90</u>	<u>180</u>	<u>50</u>	<u>5-6</u>	<u>OFF</u>	
				START RUN 5-2					
<u>123220</u>	<u>37</u>	<u>3000</u>		<u>270</u>	<u>180</u>	<u>50</u>	<u>5-7</u>	<u>OFF</u>	
				END RUN 5-2					
<u>123737</u>	<u>38</u>	<u>3000</u>							
				START RUN 5-3					
<u>123854</u>	<u>39</u>	<u>3000</u>		<u>090</u>	<u>190</u>	<u>47</u>	<u>5-7</u>	<u>OFF</u>	
				END RUN 5-3					
<u>124402</u>	<u>40</u>	<u>3000</u>							

Video Tape
 No. A462 #2
 Ends 1545
 FFC / DFC / RFC

	GPS	INU
Lat		
Long		
Time		
Status		

DRS recording to HORACE (y) n
 HORACE recording to disc (y) n
 SATCOM sending pos reports (y) n

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/ Sea st.
			START			RUN	6-1		
124553	41	3500		270	180	8-9	-3-7	OFF	
			END				61		
125044	42	3500							
			START			RUN	6-2		
125207	43	3500		090	180	9-3	-5-8	OFF	
			END			RUN	62		
125733	44	3500		090	185	9-3	-5-2	OFF	
			START			RUN	63		
125838	45	3500		270	180			OFF	
			END			RUN	63		
130400	46	3500		270	165				
			START			RUN	7-1		
130837	47	2300		100	190	7-0	5-9	OFF	
			END			RUN	7-1		
131417	48	2200							
			START			RUN	7-2		
131535	50	1900		270	185	8-1	7-2	OFF	
			END			RUN			
132033	51	1900		270	185	8-1	6-8	OFF	

Flight Leader's In-Flight Log

Flight No A A462

Date 26/6/96

Page 3 of 3

Video Tape
No. <u>A462#2</u>
Ends <u>1545</u>
FFC / DFC / RFC

	GPS	INU
Lat		
Long		
Time		
Status		

DRS recording to HORACE ☒ y/n
HORACE recording to disc ☒ y/n
SATCOM sending pos. reports ☐ y/n

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/ Sea st.	
				<u>START</u>		<u>RUN</u>	<u>7.3</u>			
<u>13223</u>	<u>52</u>	<u>1400</u>		<u>090</u>	<u>185</u>	<u>8.2</u>	<u>6.4</u>	<u>OFF</u>		
				<u>END</u>		<u>RUN</u>	<u>7.3</u>			
<u>132804</u>	<u>53</u>	<u>1400</u>		<u>090</u>	<u>180</u>	<u>8.2</u>	<u>6.4</u>	<u>OFF</u>		
				<u>START</u>		<u>RUN</u>	<u>8.1</u>			
<u>134024</u>	<u>55</u>	<u>2400</u>		<u>090</u>	<u>185</u>	<u>7.6</u>	<u>6.3</u>	<u>OFF</u>		
				<u>END</u>		<u>RUN</u>	<u>8.1</u>			
<u>134524</u>	<u>56</u>	<u>2000</u>		<u>090</u>	<u>185</u>	<u>7.4</u>	<u>6.1</u>	<u>OFF</u>		
				<u>START</u>		<u>RUN</u>	<u>8.2</u>			
<u>134856</u>	<u>57</u>	<u>2000</u>		<u>270</u>	<u>180</u>	<u>7.6</u>	<u>6.0</u>	<u>OFF</u>		
				<u>END</u>		<u>RUN</u>	<u>8.2</u>			
<u>135200</u>	<u>58</u>	<u>2000</u>		<u>270</u>	<u>180</u>	<u>7.6</u>	<u>6.1</u>	<u>OFF</u>		
				<u>START</u>		<u>RUN</u>	<u>8.3</u>			
<u>135320</u>	<u>59</u>	<u>2000</u>		<u>090</u>	<u>180</u>	<u>7.7</u>	<u>6.1</u>	<u>OFF</u>		
				<u>END</u>		<u>RUN</u>	<u>6.3</u>	<u>OFF</u>		
<u>135820</u>	<u>60</u>	<u>2000</u>		<u>090</u>	<u>180</u>	<u>7.4</u>	<u>6.7</u>	<u>OFF</u>		
				<u>NO 2 ENGINE FAULT</u>						
				<u>RETURN TO B.O.</u>						
<u>155323</u>				<u>LAND B.O.</u>						

Video Tape
No.
Ends
FFC / DFC / RFC

	GPS	INU
Lat		
Long		
Time		
Status		

DRS recording to HORACE	y/n
HORACE recording to disc	y/n
SATCOM sending pos reports	y/n

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr	625	Wind/ Sea st.
160022				51°09.70		1°44.65				GPS

SAFIRE OPERATOR'S LOG

Flight Number: A462

Operators name: JIM/JAN

Date: 26/6/96

Page 1 of

Time (GMT)	Event mark	Run no.	Height	Filter posn.	Mir-ror posn.	Shutter status		Hor link (tick)	Temp diff Ref-BB	Sol Zen	Comments
						up	low				
083000											AUTO CAL PROGRAM (COLD TARGET / EX TARGET 60°)
											STARTED
084000											END CAL
0950				0	HRS	S	S	✓			
095440			FL220	F013	ZEN	S	S			39	CLEAR ABOVE
0957											CUMULUS TO FL240
100200			FL240	F013	ZEN	S	S				CLEAR ABOVE
100345			FL240	F0	ZEN	S	S			39	CLEAR ABOVE RUN 1 STARTED
100800			FL240	F1	ZEN	S	S			39	CLEAR ABOVE
101014			FL240	F2	ZEN	S	S				CLEAR
101317			FL240	F3	ZEN	S	S				CLEAR
101445											CLOUD ABOVE
101610			FL240	F013	CADDS	S	S				INTERNAL CAL - CLOUD ABOVE
102140			FL240	F013	H013	S	S				INTERNAL CAL / UNDER CIRCUS
102215			FL240	F0	ZEN	0	S				CLEAR ABOVE LW CAL?
103321			FL240	F1	ZEN	0	S				THIN C.
103411			FL240	F2	ZEN	0	S				"
103505			FL240	F3	ZEN	0	S				"
103840			FL240	F013	C60						UNDER CIRCUS
104550			FL240	F013	H013	S	S				CIRCUS ABOVE
105230			FL240	F0	ZEN	0	S			30	CLEAR ABOVE & BELOW

SW CAL

A462

CCNC Log

GMT	ALL.EV.		Height	Dyn	STATIC							Remarks
	On	Off			1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
					1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5			PRE FLIGHT
082010	082210		0		0.11							S
082010	082210				0							D ADJUST
					0							B BASELINE
					2362							R
					972.6							P
												PRE FLIGHT
			0		0.11	0.24	0.47	0.71	1.20			S
SAME					206	240	276	297	498			D SAME
SAMPLE					256	239	244	236	240			B SAMPLE
					2393	2400	2429	2426	2450			R
					972.5	972.7	972.7	972.7	972.8			P
					1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5			PRE FLIGHT
083830	084030		0		0.11	0.23	0.47	0.69	1.17			S
					227	255	241	293	376			D
					235	235	226	222	219			B
					2458	2455	2451	2444	2454			R
					972.6	972.6	972.9	972.9	973.0			P
095550	095750	22000			0.10	0.21	0.43	0.64	1.09			S
		-24000			191	187	186	203	214			D
					192	191	190	185	186			B
					2509	2505	2502	2502	200			R
					863.9	802.4	809.0	815.4	820.7			P
					1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5			RUN 1
103410	103620	24000			0.11	0.23	0.45	0.66	1.14			S
					219	216	245	204	268			D
					235	234	232	211	207			B
					2470	2487	2487	2485	2485			R
					841.9	841.5	841.6	841.6	841.7			P
												RUN 3.1
113815	114015	100			0.10	0.22	0.43	0.65	1.09			S
					209	206	205	204	248			D
					230	216	225	223	220			B
					2500	2499	2493	2495	2498			R
					1004.9	1005.6	1003.7	1005.4	1005.3			P

OZONE ANALYZER LOG

Project: NERC (MADEHEAD) Date: 26/6/96

User: Jess Lever

Flight No: A462

Page 1 of

SPAN=504 OFFSET=50

GMT	RUN #	HEIGHT	OZONE	SCALE	REMARKS (e.g. changes in pressure)
09:45:30	Transit	178 ft.	28.57.		Not too noisy cell.
09:48:40					Set PC time & date logger.
09:53:18	Transit	21800 ft.	63		Ozone much higher here.
09:56:00	" "	22100 ft.	42.		Ozone dropping off.
10:08:09	" "	24000'	29		Ozone a bit noisy. Stop/start pump.
10:13:30	" "	24000'	32		Ozone noise much better now.
11:13:00	sp1	18000'			Interesting ozone oscillation.
11:14	"	16300			Structure of FADS with ozone.
12:04:38					
12:46:00		3500'	41.51		Step increase in ozone from 230 ppb.
13:07:36		2300	28		Drop in ozone as we drop down.
13:35.					Start of increase in O ₃ above clouds.
13:39.					Decrease in O ₃ .
14:13:48	Transit	7000'	64.5		Increase in O ₃ and decrease CO.

0

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. A462

Date: 21/6/96

 Operator: *mf*

Page 2 of 4

G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP			2D-C			HVPS / 2D-P			REMARKS
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Conc/cc	Max Size	RelT	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m ³	Max Size	Habit	
122000	140	0.11	0.7	5								
122345												
122522												end of Run
122600	240	0.37	150	25	7.0	3	50	12				Start Run 5.1 @ 2950'
122800	140	0.35	150	30	6.0	3	25	10				
123000	250	0.44	190	30	7.1	3	50	10				
123008												
133222	140											end of Run
133300	140	0.38	140	30	5.9	3	50	12				Start Run 5.2 @ 2950'
133500	90	0.35	140	30	5.5	2	50	12				
133700	170	0.45	180	25	7.1	2	50	10				
133837												end of Run
123900	125	0.36	150	35	7.2	4	50	10				Start Run 5.3 @ 2950'
124100	90	0.26	145	30	5	3	50	10				
124300	215	0.36	180	35	6.5	0.5	25	12				
124408	210	0.4										
124553												end of Run
124600	80	0.10										Start Run 6.1 @ 3500'
124800	100	0.10										
125043												end of Run
125212												Start Run 6.2 @ 3500'
125300	90	0.10										
125500	130	0.11										
125700	110	0.11										
125931												end of Run
125859												Start Run 6.3 @ 3500'
125900	100	0.10										
130100	100	0.11										
130300	115	0.10										
130400												end of Run
130537												Start Run 7.1 @ 2900'
130900	140	0.11	0.7	10								
131100	137	0.12	0.7	10								
131300	160	0.12										
131416												end of Run
131536												Start Run 7.2 @ 1900'

DATE 26 JUN 96 TI MRF 01NAV S/L AMERSAIRFIELD BOSCOMBE DOWN

AIRFIELD _____

R/W 23 W/V 300/05 TEMP 17 QNH 1022 QFE 1008R/W 23 W/V 320/07 TEMP _____ QNH 1022 QFE 1008WX No SIC

WX _____

ATC CL WEST 1220 SA 3322 STUO 4

ATC CL _____

T/O TIME 0929LAND TIME 1554

TIME	HDG	DR	G/S	IAS	TAS	W/V	ALT/FL	QNH/PR	LAT/LONG		RUN
1004 ⁰⁷	290	3 1/2 P	266	196	289	324/30	F240	1024	N 5155.7	W 00444.1	R1
1038 ²¹							F240		N 5240.7	W 00846.5	ER1
1040 ⁴⁷	253	4P	274	199	291	287/30	F240	✓	N 5240.8	W 00902.6	R2
1105 ¹⁶							F240		N 5200.5	W 01153.8	ER2
1107 ²⁸	185	5P	274	180	267	280/31	F240	✓	N 5155.2	W 01203.7	P1
1133 ²⁰									_____		IP1
1134 ¹³									N 5019.4	W 01200.2	RP1
1136 ³⁰								1029	N 5026.0	W 01201.7	RP1
1138 ⁰⁴	085	3S	180	176	175	091/6	100'	✓	N 5028.6	W 01157.9	SR3.1
1143 ⁰⁵								✓	N 5030.0	W 01133.9	ER3.1
1145 ⁰²	267	3P	181	181	180	352/10	100'		N 5031.6	W 01135.3	SR3.2
1153 ²¹								✓	N 5023.9	W 01212.6	ER3.2
1155 ¹⁶	078	3S	189	188	186	354/03	100		N 5021.6	W 01209.5	SR3.3
1202 ¹⁶								✓	N 5024.0	W 01136.5	ER3.3
1204 ¹⁴	267	3P	188	180	186	351/11	2600	✓	N 5021.5	W 01137.9	SR4.1
1209 ¹⁷									N 5019.3	W 01202.4	ER4.1
1211 ³⁵	081	2S	186	178	182	343/8	✓	✓	N 5021.9	W 01201.4	SR4.2
1216 ³⁶									N 5023.9	W 01137.3	ER4.2
1218 ⁴⁵	245	3P	193	183	189	345/12	✓	✓	N 5025.6	W 01139.3	SR4.3
1223 ⁴⁵								✓	N 5017.7	W 01201.0	ER4.3
1225 ³⁰	082	4S	186	178	182	018/09	3000	✓	N 5015.8	W 01158.2	SR5.1
1230 ⁵⁴									N 5018.3	W 01132.4	ER5.1
1232 ²⁰	266	3P	186	182	187	359/12	✓	✓	N 5016.3	W 01132.2	SR5.2

TIME	HDG	DR	G/S	IAS	TAS	W/V	ALT/FL	QNH/PR	LAT / LONG	RUN
1237 ³⁷							3000	1029	N 5014.5 W 01157.8	ER5.2
1238 ⁵⁹	080	2LS	186	184	191	026/08	/	/	N 5012.3 W 01157.6	SR5.3
1244 ⁰²							/	/	N 5015.1 W 01133.8	ER5.3
1245 ⁴³	264	2LP	189	181	189	358/10	3500	/	N 5012.0 W 01133.3	SR6.1
1250 ⁴⁴							/	/	N 5010.2 W 01157.2	ER6.1
1252 ⁰⁷	079	2S	196	181	190	094/01	/	/	N 5007.9 W 01156.5	SR6.2
1257 ³³							/	/	N 5011.0 W 01129.6	ER6.2
1258 ⁵⁸	264	2LP	188	178	186	321/04	/	/	N 5008.7 W 01129.3	SR6.3
1304 ⁰¹								/	N 5006.6 W 01153.7	ER6.3
1308 ³⁷	091	3S	193	185	190	327/02	2300	/	N 4954.1 W 01140.3	SR7.1
1314 ¹⁷								/	N 4953.8 W 01112.9	ER7.1
1315 ³⁵	264	2LP	183	180	182	326/05	1900	/	N 4951.4 W 01113.0	SR7.2
1320 ⁵³								/	N 4949.1 W 01138.2	ER7.2
1322 ²³	090	2LS	189	184	186	348/05	1900	/	N 4946.8 W 01137.5	SR7.3
1328 ⁰⁴								/	N 4945.9 W 01109.9	ER7.3
1340 ²⁴	081	3LS	185	184	187	011/08	2000	/	N 4920.7 W 01126.1	SR8.1
1345 ²⁴							/	/	N 4922.9 W 01102.9	ER8.1
1346 ⁵⁶	265	41	186	182	184	000/09	/	/	N 4925.2 W 01104.1	SR8.2
1352 ⁰⁰							/	/	N 4922.5 W 01128.1	ER8.2
1353 ²⁰	076	3LS	176	175	178	005/14	/	/	N 4920.9 W 01126.4	SR8.3
1358 ²⁰									N 4923.2 W 01103.8	ER8.3
NO2 ENGINE / PROPELLER PITCH LOCKED										

Diversion : 1000
 Min Overhead : 5700
 Contingency : 1635
 Extra Fuel : 0
 Req'd Start Fuel: 42037

Actual Reserve : 16298
 Hold Fuel Flow : 4500
 Rsv Endurance : 3.37
 Flt Plan Time : 6.38
 Total Endurance: 10.15

ZFW : 38000
 Ramp Fuel : 50000
 Ramp Weight : 146000
 Take Off Weight: 145000
 Landing Weight : 112298

(c) RJCV 1991

WAYPOINTS			OBSERVATIONS
EGDM	00407'	N5109.5 W00144.3	1
WESTPT		N5110.0 W00210.0	2
BRI	380.00	N5122.8 W00243.0	
BCN	117.45	N5143.5 W00315.7	3
AMMAN		N5150.4 W00359.8	
STU	113.10	N5159.7 W00502.3	4
SLANY		N5209.5 W00550.6	
CML	387.00	N5227.2 W00728.8	
SHA	113.30	N5243.5 W00853.2	5
DOLIP		N5200.0 W01200.0	6
GIPER		N5100.0 W01200.0	7
KENUK		N5000.0 W01200.0	8
SON11W		N5000.0 W01100.0	9
SON10W		N5000.0 W01000.0	10
SON09W		N5000.0 W00900.0	11
GAPLI		N5000.0 W00800.0	12
LND	114.20	N5008.1 W00538.2	13
EX	337.00	N5045.1 W00317.6	14
EGDM	00407'	N5109.5 W00144.3	1
EGDL	00513'	N5130.6 W00159.4	0

VACC in-flight log

Flight No: A462 Date: 26/06/96.

Operator: O'SBORNE / M. RILEY

Project: ^{o' down} MAGE/ACSUE . Tube Temperature settings: A= 30°C B= 80°C C= 150°C D= 300°C PAGE 1/5

GMT	Laser volts	Tube	Run	VACC event	Height	Comments (e.g. comparisons with PCASP, aerosol sources/observations, pollution, problems with RDAS timeouts)
~0930						T/O from BUSCOMB DOWN.
0930						RDAS TIMING UP PROBLEM ON BOOT - UP.
						COMMS PROBLEM - TYPE "C" MODE COM1: 96n, 8"
~0945	7.5	1	T	WUP	P190	SOFTWARE UP + RUNNING - "A462-2.DAS"
094732		1				DATA VALID.
094820		1				RDAS TIMED - OUT BRIEFLY - OK (?)
0954		1			P220	Increased counts - haze layer.
095630		2			Rising	Tube 2 counts / counts dropped off. (coming out haze layer?)
100130	6.0	3			P240	Tube 3. Very low counts. INVALID FOR 2300hrs
100415						Run 1 start - STABLE RUNS. Ignore?
100700	6.5	4	1	-	P240	Tube 4. Counts virtually zero now. PCASP also
101228	7.0	1	1	-	P240	Tube 1. One w. low counts. A little higher than H ₂ O
1036						Plate counting in 2 second intervals (not 1) now
1056						Had been in "ascent" for unknown period up to this time.
110730	7.5	1	PIV	-	P240	Profile descent. Tube 1

VACC in-flight log

Flight No: A662

Date: 26/06/96

Operator: O'SURVEY/m. P. Curran

Project: O'Donoghue

Tube Temperature settings: A=35°C B=80°C C=150°C D=300°C

PAGE 2/5

GMT	Laser volts	Tube	Run	VACC event	Height	Comments (e.g. comparisons with PCASP, aerosol sources/observations, pollution, problems with RDAS timeouts)
7114		1	P1 ↓		FL160	haze layer? + rising.
7118	9.0V-	1	P1 ↓		FL30	Start below haze layer.
1120		1	P1		FL100	digital count. PCASP ~ 1000/cc.
1123	9.5V	1	P1		480'	Counts dropping off.
112900		1	P1		3,300'	hit cloud.
113072	9.1	1	P1		2,600'	Just back of S-Cu. PCASP ~ 180/cc.
113320			P1 →		1000'	Interrupt profile.
113412	9.1	1	P1 ↓		1000'	Re-start profile descent.
113630	9.1	1	P1		50'	End profile.
113802	9.1	1	3.1	#1	100'	Start run.
114309	9.1	1	3.1	#2	100'	End run + change TUBE #3
114502	9	3	3.2	#3	100'	Start run TUBE 3
115320	9	3	3.2	#4	100'	End run change TUBE #4
115522	9	4	3.3	#6	1100'	Start run TUBE 4 some pink color seen mostly small sect?
120210		4	3.3	#7	100'	End run → Ascend (in bell)

VACC in-flight log

Flight No: A462

Date: 26/6/96

Operator: OSBORN / M. FULFORD

Project: O'Donnell

Tube Temperature settings: A= 30°C B= 80°C C= 150°C D= 300°C

PAGE 3 / 5

GMT	Laser volts	Tube	Run	VACC event	Height	Comments (e.g. comparisons with PCASP, aerosol sources/observations, pollution, problems with RDAS timeouts)
120414	9.2	1	4.1	8	2600'	Start Run @ correct height level. Below cloud base
120916	9.1	1	4.1	9	2600'	End Run. → Tube 3 change.
121140	9	3	4.2	10	2600'	Start Run. PCASP ~ 130/cc
121634	9	3	4.2	11	2600'	End Run. → change to Tube 4.
121846	9	4	4.3	12	2600'	Start Run. Some haze - FSSP (?)
122343	9	4	4.3	13	2600'	End Run. → change to Tube 1
122530	9	1	5.1	14	3000'	(rise into cloud.) Start Run in haze
123000	9	1	5.1	15	3000'	End Run, select Tube 3
123218	9	3	5.2	16	3000'	Start Run,
123738	9	3	5.2	17	3000'	End Run, select Tube 4.
123857	9	4	5.3	18	3000ft	Start Run,
124030		4				Going through hole in the cloud
124400	9	4	5.3	19	3000ft	End Run, select Tube 1 climb out of cloud
124557	9	1	6.1	20	3500ft	Start Run above cloud PCASP = 100
125042	9	01	6.1	21	3500ft	End Run, select Tube 3

VACC in-flight log

Flight No: A46Z Date: 28/6/96

Operator: OSBORN/M. RING

Project: OSD

Tube Temperature settings: A= 30°C B= 80°C C= 150°C D= 300°C PAGE 4/5

GMT	Laser volts	Tube	Run	VACC event	Height	Comments (e.g. comparisons with PCASP, aerosol sources/observations, pollution, problems with RDAS timeouts)
125204	9	3	6.2	22	3500ft	Start Run PCASP ≈ 100 /cc
125734	9	3	6.2	23	3900ft	End Run, select Tube 4
125856	9	4	6.3	24	3520ft	Start Run, PCASP ≈ 90 /cc
130400	9	4	6.3	25	3500ft	End Run, select Tube 1, descend + head downwind
130836	9	1	7.1	26	2380ft	Start Run, under cloud PCASP ≈ 140 /cc
131220	9	1	7.1	27	2000ft	End Run, select Tube 3 - 131333 descend a little & stay under cloud.
131532	9	3	7.2	28	2000ft ¹⁹	Start Run PCASP ≈ 130 /cc
132050	9	3	7.2	29	1900'	End Run, change → Tube #4
132222	9	4	7.3	30	1900'	Start Run
132802	9	4	7.3	31	1700'	End Run, change → Tube #1, Transit
134023	9	1	8.1	32	2000ft	Start Run, below cloud base
134526	9	1	8.1	33	2000ft	End Run, select Tube 3 PCASP ≈ 140 /cc
134654	9	3	8.2	34	2000ft	Start Run PCASP ≈ 150
135203	9	3	8.2	35	2000ft	End Run, select Tube 4
135320	9	4	8.3	36	2000ft	Start Run PCASP ≈ 140 /cc

FLIGHT LEADER'S INSTRUMENT STATUS REPORT
 =====

FLIGHT NO: *A462*

DATE: *26/6/96*

MRF

INSTRUMENT	FITTED		OPERATED		COMMENTS
	YES	NO	YES	NO	
NAVIGATION:					
GPS	/				
OMEGA	/				
INU	/				
RADALT	/				
THERMOMETERS:					
DI TEMP	/				
NDI TEMP	/				
ICTP					
BARNES PRT4	<i>HEIKAN</i>				
HYGROMETERS:					
GEN. EASTERN	/				
TWC	/				
FWVS	/		/		
J/W	/				
EXP. PITOT HEAD:					
STATIC PRESS.	/				
PITOT PRESS.	/				
GUST VANES	/				
RADIOMETERS:					
UPPER CLEAR	/				
UPPER RED	/				
UPPER SILICON	/				
LOWER CLEAR	/				
LOWER RED	/				
LOWER SILICON	/				
MARSS			/		
MCR/SAFIRE	/				
DEIMOS					
CHEMISTRY:					
OZONE	/				
ECGC		/			
NOX		/			
OTHERS:					
CCN	/				
CLOUD PHYSICS	/				
CABIN PRESS	/				
NEPHELOMETER	/				
HOLOGRAPHY		/			

E.R. MONITOR PRODUCED SYNC FAULT
ON PRINTER WHEN PRINTING.

No. 2 Engine prop pitch locked
Scribe aborted.

INSTRUMENT STATUS AND REQUIREMENT FORM
A462 26JUN96 MRF

STANDARD INSTRUMENTS			
EXP PIT STAT HEAD			
Pitot-static	On	Ess	
Wind Vanes	On	Ess	
THERMOMETERS			
ICTP	X		
De-iced	On		
Non De-iced	On	Ess	
HYGROMETERS			
Gen East (1011)	On	Ess	
Fluor W V S	On	Des	
AEROSOL SAMPLING			
Filters	X		
CN Counter	X		
VACC	On	Ess	
PSAP	On	Des	
CVI	X		
Alleviator	On	Des	
CCN	On	Des	
Nephelometer	On	Des	
CHEMICAL			
TECO Ozone	On		
Bendix Ozone (eth)	X		
ECGC's	X		
UEA Peroxide	X		
KFA	On		
IMAGERY			
Weather Radar	On	Ess	
Video Cameras	On	Des	
Video Rec	On	Des	
Photo Cameras	On	Des	
Hand Held Video	On	Des	
DATA RECORDING			
Video printer	On	Des	
Horace	On	Ess	
DRS	On	Ess	

NAVIGATION/AIRCRAFT PERFORMANCE			
INS	On	Ess	
GPS	On	Ess	
Mag compass	On	Ess	
Omega	On	Ess	
radar Alt	On	Ess	
CLOUD PHYSICS			
PCASP	On	Des	
2D CLOUD	On	Des	
FSSP	X	Des	**
HVPS	On		
JW	On	Des	
Tot Water	On	Des	
DROPSONDE SYSTEM			
Sondes	On		
Receivers	On		
RADIOMETERS			
Deimos	On		
Heimann	On	Ess	
BROAD BAND LOWER			
Standard Fit	On	Ess	
Non standard	X		
BROAD BAND UPPER			
Standard fit	X	Ess****	
Non standard	X		
Obscurers (L)	X		
Obscurers (S)	X	Ess****	
NARROW BAND			
Marss	X		
MCR/SAFIRE	X	Des	**

R : Remove, C : Cover
T/O TIME - 10:30 local

A462

26-JUN-96

09:58:21

012 Ω

51.84

-4.12 AS P

HDG deg T	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
288.	398.	23.7	237.	-25.2	-47.8	332/12

OZONE MR
ppb

58.36

125.00

100.00

75.00

50.00

25.00

0.00

125.00

100.00

75.00

50.00

25.00

0.00

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

A462 26-JUN-96 09:59:57 012 Ω 51.87 -4.28 RV P

HDG	SPR	PHGT	TAS	TAT	DEW	WIND
deg T	mb	kft	knots	C	C	deg m/s
288.	392.	24.0	249.	-25.7	-46.5	326/13

OZONE MR 62.27 GE DEWP -46.54
ppb C

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

A462 26-JUN-96 10:02:57 012 Ω 51.92 -4.61 RV

HDG degT	SPR mb	PRGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
290.	392.	24.1	284.	-25.4	-40.2	324/15

OZONE MR 49.57 CO MR 314.00
ppb ppb

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

A462 26-JUN-96 11:25:03 017 50.78 -12.00 RV P

HDC	SPR	FWGT	TAS	TAT	DEW	WIND
deg F	mb	kft	knots	C	C	deg m/s
182.	824.	5.6	198.	9.6	-26.3	289/4

OZONE MR 58.85 CO MR 227.00
ppb ppb

A B C D E F G H
SELECT PARAS FREQ ZOOM

A462 26-JUN-96 11:26:39 018 Ω 50.69 -12.00 AS P

HDG deg T	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
181.	864.	4.3	206.	7.6	-12.4	316 / 4

GE DP

TWC DP

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SEARCH	INDEX	VIDEO	HELP				

A462 26-JUN-96 11:28:21 018 Q 50.59 -12.00 RV P

HGT degT	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
183.	894.	3.4	194.	8.0	-5.4	351/3

PRES HGT 1046.50 m OZONE MR 43.47 ppb CO MR 233.00 ppb

0.00 100.00 200.00 300.00 400.00 500.00

A B C D E F G H

A462 26-JUN-96 11:37:09 021 Ω 50.48 -12.06 AS P

HDG deg T	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
29.	1015.	0.0	185.	12.5	6.8	025/4

GE DP

TWC DP

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FILE	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

PCASP CONC/cc

500

PCASP CONC #/cc 160
 PCASP MEAN RAD um 0.1
 PCASP MASS ug/m3 17.30

FSSP CONC #/cc 1
 FSSP MEAN RAD u 2.4
 FSSP LWC gm/m3 0.00

2D-C CONC #/l 0.0
 2D-C MAX SIZE um 0
 2D-C LWC g/m3 0.000e+000

96-06-26 13:48:24

PCASP COUNT FSSP COUNT

1000
1000

1
1

0.1
0.1

10
10

A462

26-JUN-96

13:49:27

057 Ω

49.39

-11.28 FC P

HDG degT 264.	SPR mb 955.	PHGT kft 1.6	TAS knots 189.	TAT C 7.6	DEW C 6.7	WIND deg m/s 009/7	
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— PLOT 5 134241

A SELECT	B CCNMEN	C HOLD	D	E	F	G VIDEO	H
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LIST OF FORMS USED ON FLIGHT

No. of forms	Form Title
	Aircraft Scientist de-briefing sheet Aircraft Scientist log Aircraft Scientist post flight requirements sheet Interactive log
	Flight Leader pre-flight check form Flight Leader in-flight check form Flight Leader in-flight log Flight Leader Video tape log (photocopy original)
	SAFIRE log CCN log MARSS log DEIMOS log Chemistry log
	Particulate / Filter boom Operator's log 2DC / FSSP / Holography Operator's log Sonde Ejector's log Navigator's log Photographic log (photocopy original)
	Instrument status forms RTD prints Raw data plots Weather charts Satellite pictures GPS track

	<p>...</p>
	<p>...</p>
	<p>...</p>
	<p>...</p>
	<p>...</p>
<p>... ...</p>	<p>...</p>

A462 26-JUN-96

Run no. R_all

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 730
No. of obs 10253
Mean 50.2132
Standard dev 0.532486
Max value 51.9186
Min value 49.3456

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 731
No. of obs 10253
Mean -11.6960
Standard dev 0.301309
Max value -11.0109
Min value -12.2471

CORRECTED NORTH VEL (M S-1)

Parameter no. 735
No. of obs 10253
Mean -27.4159
Standard dev 53.5480
Max value 107.987
Min value -146.916

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96

Run no. R_all

CORRECTED EAST VEL (M S-1)

Parameter no. 736
No. of obs 10253
Mean 7.00375
Standard dev 80.7413
Max value 119.115
Min value -123.569

DEICED IND TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 519
No. of obs 10253
Mean 284.876
Standard dev 5.29930
Max value 292.809
Min value 258.074

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 520
No. of obs 10253
Mean 280.097
Standard dev 5.97822
Max value 286.545
Min value 248.973

11:07:28 11:50:11 12:32:54 13:15:37 13:58:20
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96

Run no. R_all

NON-DEICED IND TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 524
No. of obs 10253
Mean 284.809
Standard dev 5.28772
Max value 292.735
Min value 257.900

NON-DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 525
No. of obs 10253
Mean 279.889
Standard dev 5.99221
Max value 286.337
Min value 248.537

SURFACE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 537
No. of obs 10253
Mean 285.242
Standard dev 2.59144
Max value 288.244
Min value 277.269

1 second averages

TIME (GMT)

A462 26-JUN-96

Run no. R_all

TOTAL WATER CONTENT (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 572
No. of obs 10253
Mean 4.91050
Standard dev 1.91658
Max value 6.89643
Min value 0.119022

DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 529
No. of obs 10253
Mean 273.982
Standard dev 10.1066
Max value 286.594
Min value 234.453

TOTAL WATER DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 725
No. of obs 10253
Mean 273.400
Standard dev 11.1256
Max value 281.068
Min value 226.406

1 second averages

11:07:28 11:50:11 12:32:54 13:15:37 13:58:20
TIME (GMT)

A462 26-JUN-96

Run no. R_all

J/W LWC (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 535
No. of obs 10253
Mean 0.107031
Standard dev 5.533877e-02
Max value 0.511221
Min value -8.746376e-02

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

Parameter no. 576
No. of obs 10253
Mean 912.893
Standard dev 122.989
Max value 1026.42
Min value 393.464

PITOT-STATIC PRESSUR (MB)

Parameter no. 577
No. of obs 10253
Mean 56.9657
Standard dev 9.77633
Max value 124.641
Min value 38.2728

1 second averages

11:07:28 11:50:11 12:32:54 13:15:37 13:58:20
TIME (GMT)

A462 26-JUN-96

Run no. R_all

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578
No. of obs 10253
Mean 951.391
Standard dev 1345.86
Max value 7301.58
Min value -109.031

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 575
No. of obs 10253
Mean 597.298
Standard dev 396.135
Max value 1522.15
Min value 0.000000

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

Parameter no. 574
No. of obs 10253
Mean 0.000000
Standard dev 0.000000
Max value 0.000000
Min value 0.000000

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96

Run no. R_all

UPP VIS CLR SIG (W M-2)

Parameter no. 673
No. of obs 10253
Mean 835.791
Standard dev 160.715
Max value 1255.45
Min value 365.535

UPP VIS RED SIG (W M-2)

Parameter no. 674
No. of obs 10253
Mean 403.649
Standard dev 86.8705
Max value 602.446
Min value 153.153

UPP I/R SIGNAL (W M-2)

Parameter no. 675
No. of obs 10253
Mean 423.826
Standard dev 53.3387
Max value 576.098
Min value 257.020

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96

Run no. R_all

LWR VIS CLR SIG (WM-2)

Parameter no. 682
No. of obs 10253
Mean 135.566
Standard dev 76.7879
Max value 558.468
Min value 71.3710

LWR VIS RED SIG (WM-2)

Parameter no. 683
No. of obs 10253
Mean 66.3501
Standard dev 39.0779
Max value 282.560
Min value 34.7766

LWR I/R SIGNAL (WM-2)

Parameter no. 684
No. of obs 10253
Mean 47.1915
Standard dev 26.6323
Max value 169.725
Min value 16.0715

11:07:28 11:50:11 12:32:54 13:15:37 13:58:20

TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96

Run no. R_all

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 901
No. of obs 10253
Mean 21.2320
Standard dev 50.6676
Max value 256.963
Min value 0.000000

FSSP MEAN RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 902
No. of obs 10253
Mean 3.35805
Standard dev 2.14367
Max value 8.55288
Min value 0.000000

FSSP LWC (G M-3)

Parameter no. 903
No. of obs 10253
Mean 2.214897e-02
Standard dev 5.341204e-02
Max value 0.620207
Min value 0.000000

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96

Run no. R_all

FSSP MEAN VOL. RAD. (MICRON)

Parameter no. 904
No. of obs 10253
Mean 3.65881
Standard dev 2.30501
Max value 9.72057
Min value 0.000000

FSSP MEAN AREAL RAD. (MICRON)

Parameter no. 905
No. of obs 10253
Mean 3.51153
Standard dev 2.23851
Max value 8.78825
Min value 0.000000

FSSP EFF. RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 906
No. of obs 10253
Mean 3.99140
Standard dev 2.49144
Max value 13.7332
Min value 0.000000

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96

Run no. R_all

PCASP MEAN VOL. RAD. (MICRON)

Parameter no. 922
No. of obs 10253
Mean 0.224811
Standard dev 0.182737
Max value 0.906848
Min value 6.766292e-02

PCASP MEAN VOL. RAD. (MICRON)

PCASP MEAN AREAL RAD (MICRON)

Parameter no. 923
No. of obs 10253
Mean 0.177068
Standard dev 0.142612
Max value 0.797960
Min value 6.639692e-02

PCASP MEAN AREAL RAD (MICRON)

PCASP EFF. RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 924
No. of obs 10253
Mean 0.382345
Standard dev 0.328026
Max value 1.23146
Min value 7.023311e-02

PCASP EFF. RADIUS (MICRON)

11:07:28 11:50:11 12:32:54 13:15:37 13:58:20
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96 Profile P1

Times 11:07:28-11:36:30 GMT

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96 Profile P1

Times 11:07:28-11:36:30 GMT

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96 Profile P1

Times 11:07:28-11:36:30 GMT

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96 Profile P1

Times 11:07:28-11:36:30 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96 Profile P1

Times 11:07:28-11:36:30 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96 Profile P1

Times 11:07:28-11:36:30 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96 Profile P1

Times 11:07:28-11:36:30 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96 Profile P1

Times 11:07:28-11:36:30 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96 Profile P1

Times 11:07:28-11:36:30 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96 Profile P1

Times 11:07:28-11:36:30 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96 Profile P1

Times 11:07:28-11:36:30 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96

Run no. R3

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

No. of obs 1453
Mean 266.755
Standard dev 137.285
Max value 359.994
Min value 0.122260

WIND SPEED (METRES/S)

No. of obs 1453
Mean 3.66803
Standard dev 1.22460
Max value 6.62654
Min value 0.752584

WIND COMP (METRES/s)

Parameter no. 714,715
No. of obs 1453
Mean north -3.42166
Stan dev north 1.29642
Max north -0.724825
Min north -6.58929
Mean east -3.42166
Stan dev east 1.29642
Max east -0.724825
Min east -6.58929

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96

Run no. R3

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 730
No. of obs 1453
Mean 50.4504
Standard dev 5.820254e-02
Max value 50.5320
Min value 50.3540

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 731
No. of obs 1453
Mean -11.8673
Standard dev 0.206206
Max value -11.5165
Min value -12.2471

CORRECTED NORTH VEL (M S-1)

Parameter no. 735
No. of obs 1453
Mean -5.94034
Standard dev 29.4077
Max value 86.0926
Min value -101.545

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96

Run no. R3

CORRECTED EAST VEL (M S-1)

Parameter no. 736
No. of obs 1453
Mean 17.5783
Standard dev 87.9626
Max value 98.1931
Min value -95.0343

DEICED IND TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 519
No. of obs 1453
Mean 290.532
Standard dev 0.270267
Max value 291.069
Min value 289.526

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 520
No. of obs 1453
Mean 286.329
Standard dev 0.218241
Max value 286.545
Min value 285.591

1 second averages

TIME (GMT)

A462 26-JUN-96

Run no. R3

NON-DEICED IND TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 524
No. of obs 1453
Mean 290.440
Standard dev 0.275107
Max value 290.981
Min value 289.398

NON-DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 525
No. of obs 1453
Mean 286.113
Standard dev 0.222221
Max value 286.337
Min value 285.354

SURFACE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 537
No. of obs 1453
Mean 285.936
Standard dev 23.8118
Max value 288.244
Min value 0.000000

1 second averages

TIME (GMT)

A462 26-JUN-96

Run no. R3

TOTAL WATER CONTENT (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 572
No. of obs 1453
Mean 5.90432
Standard dev 0.191517
Max value 6.48489
Min value 5.48077

DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 529
No. of obs 1453
Mean 280.179
Standard dev 0.455723
Max value 281.492
Min value 279.129

TOTAL WATER DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 725
No. of obs 1453
Mean 279.694
Standard dev 0.463683
Max value 281.068
Min value 278.644

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96

Run no. R3

J/W LWC (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 535
No. of obs 1453
Mean 0.107749
Standard dev 1.750168e-02
Max value 0.148839
Min value 4.205434e-02

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

Parameter no. 576
No. of obs 1453
Mean 1023.44
Standard dev 2.46532
Max value 1025.09
Min value 1014.43

PITOT-STATIC PRESSUR (MB)

Parameter no. 577
No. of obs 1453
Mean 56.0575
Standard dev 2.51798
Max value 63.3225
Min value 50.9284

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96

Run no. R3

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578
No. of obs 1453
Mean -84.4475
Standard dev 20.4039
Max value -9.81985
Min value -98.1287

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 575
No. of obs 1453
Mean 39.1926
Standard dev 20.6261
Max value 112.275
Min value 25.1099

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

Parameter no. 574
No. of obs 1453
Mean 0.000000
Standard dev 0.000000
Max value 0.000000
Min value 0.000000

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96

Run no. R3

UPP VIS CLR SIG (W M-2)

Parameter no. 673
No. of obs 1453
Mean 703.212
Standard dev 151.084
Max value 1255.45
Min value 365.535

UPP VIS RED SIG (W M-2)

Parameter no. 674
No. of obs 1453
Mean 328.066
Standard dev 77.3378
Max value 563.329
Min value 153.153

UPP I/R SIGNAL (W M-2)

Parameter no. 675
No. of obs 1453
Mean 373.530
Standard dev 53.9260
Max value 576.098
Min value 0.000000

11:38:04 11:44:07 11:50:10 11:56:13 12:02:16
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96

Run no. R3

LWR VIS CLR SIG (WM-2)

Parameter no. 682
No. of obs 1453
Mean 85.4803
Standard dev 6.43666
Max value 110.887
Min value 71.3710

LWR VIS RED SIG (WM-2)

Parameter no. 683
No. of obs 1453
Mean 44.7047
Standard dev 3.35801
Max value 58.5576
Min value 37.8451

LWR I/R SIGNAL (WM-2)

Parameter no. 684
No. of obs 1453
Mean 21.7563
Standard dev 3.66620
Max value 36.7697
Min value 16.0715

11:38:04 11:44:07 11:50:10 11:56:13 12:02:16
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A402 26-JUN-96

Run no. R3

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 901
No. of obs 1453
Mean 0.269046
Standard dev 0.141773
Max value 0.803421
Min value 2.461500e-02

FSSP MEAN RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 902
No. of obs 1453
Mean 2.12074
Standard dev 0.408501
Max value 6.25000
Min value 1.75000

FSSP LWC (G M-3)

Parameter no. 903
No. of obs 1453
Mean 1.483848e-05
Standard dev 1.414610e-05
Max value 1.547920e-04
Min value 5.526067e-07

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96

Run no. R3

FSSP MEAN VOL. RAD. (MICRON)

Parameter no. 904
No. of obs 1453
Mean 2.26635
Standard dev 0.504521
Max value 6.25145
Min value 1.75025

FSSP MEAN AREAL RAD. (MICRON)

Parameter no. 905
No. of obs 1453
Mean 2.19206
Standard dev 0.453705
Max value 6.24953
Min value 1.74999

FSSP EFF. RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 906
No. of obs 1453
Mean 2.42803
Standard dev 0.648174
Max value 6.73396
Min value 1.75008

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96

Run no. R3

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 919
No. of obs 1453
Mean 161.133
Standard dev 23.2160
Max value 240.665
Min value 95.1441

PCASP MEAN RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 920
No. of obs 1453
Mean 0.102219
Standard dev 6.262618e-03
Max value 0.128435
Min value 8.686098e-02

PCASP MASS CONTENT (G M-3)

Parameter no. 921
No. of obs 1453
Mean 4.15123
Standard dev 3.77514
Max value 28.3605
Min value 0.423856

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96

Run no. R4

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

No. of obs 1173
Mean 253.097
Standard dev 154.917
Max value 359.997
Min value 2.087308e-02

WIND SPEED (METRES/S)

No. of obs 1173
Mean 4.55602
Standard dev 0.880194
Max value 6.83054
Min value 1.83552

WIND COMP (METRES/s)

Parameter no. 714,715
No. of obs 1173
Mean north -4.48033
Stan dev north 0.895496
Max north -1.78496
Min north -6.82469
Mean east -4.48033
Stan dev east 0.895496
Max east -1.78496
Min east -6.82469

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96

Run no. R4

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 730
No. of obs 1173
Mean 50.3655
Standard dev 3.408228e-02
Max value 50.4396
Min value 50.2950

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 731
No. of obs 1173
Mean -11.8351
Standard dev 0.151712
Max value -11.5696
Min value -12.1043

CORRECTED NORTH VEL (M S-1)

Parameter no. 735
No. of obs 1173
Mean -6.03825
Standard dev 35.3589
Max value 92.6442
Min value -50.4259

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96

Run no. R4

CORRECTED EAST VEL (M S-1)

Parameter no. 736
No. of obs 1173
Mean -23.3010
Standard dev 86.2538
Max value 100.767
Min value -97.8233

DEICED IND TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 519
No. of obs 1173
Mean 283.627
Standard dev 0.190005
Max value 284.075
Min value 283.157

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 520
No. of obs 1173
Mean 279.266
Standard dev 9.703752e-02
Max value 279.528
Min value 278.874

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96

Run no. R4

NON-DEICED IND TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 524
No. of obs 1173
Mean 283.527
Standard dev 0.195962
Max value 283.968
Min value 283.048

NON-DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 525
No. of obs 1173
Mean 279.038
Standard dev 9.455103e-02
Max value 279.289
Min value 278.834

SURFACE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 537
No. of obs 1173
Mean 286.572
Standard dev 0.158619
Max value 286.949
Min value 285.557

12:04:14 12:09:07 12:14:00 12:18:53 12:23:46

1 second averages

TIME (GMT)

A462 26-JUN-96

Run no. R4

J/W LWC (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 535
No. of obs 1173
Mean 0.110499
Standard dev 1.822540e-02
Max value 0.210026
Min value 4.135213e-02

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

Parameter no. 576
No. of obs 1173
Mean 937.484
Standard dev 0.465304
Max value 939.395
Min value 936.181

PITOT-STATIC PRESSUR (MB)

Parameter no. 577
No. of obs 1173
Mean 54.6918
Standard dev 2.00334
Max value 61.3931
Min value 49.2633

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96

Run no. R4

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578
No. of obs 1173
Mean 650.687
Standard dev 4.12422
Max value 662.244
Min value 633.762

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 575
No. of obs 1173
Mean 779.861
Standard dev 3.89503
Max value 792.864
Min value 762.756

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

Parameter no. 574
No. of obs 1173
Mean 0.000000
Standard dev 0.000000
Max value 0.000000
Min value 0.000000

12:04:14 12:09:07 12:14:00 12:18:53 12:23:46
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96

Run no. R4

UPP VIS CLR SIG (W M-2)

Parameter no. 673
No. of obs 1173
Mean 814.659
Standard dev 121.597
Max value 1150.96
Min value 0.000000

UPP VIS RED SIG (W M-2)

Parameter no. 674
No. of obs 1173
Mean 392.700
Standard dev 63.1950
Max value 567.307
Min value 223.431

UPP I/R SIGNAL (W M-2)

Parameter no. 675
No. of obs 1173
Mean 417.150
Standard dev 39.1607
Max value 518.982
Min value 278.987

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96

Run no. R4

LWR VIS CLR SIG (WM-2)

Parameter no. 682
No. of obs 1173
Mean 97.3967
Standard dev 5.42366
Max value 123.790
Min value 87.5000

LWR VIS RED SIG (WM-2)

Parameter no. 683
No. of obs 1173
Mean 49.0525
Standard dev 3.74300
Max value 58.8133
Min value 43.4707

LWR I/R SIGNAL (WM-2)

Parameter no. 684
No. of obs 1173
Mean 33.1189
Standard dev 2.45186
Max value 45.0490
Min value 28.9774

12:04:14 12:09:07 12:14:00 12:18:53 12:23:46
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96

Run no. R4

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 901
No. of obs 1173
Mean 3.91414
Standard dev 18.2756
Max value 190.099
Min value 2.486940e-02

FSSP MEAN RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 902
No. of obs 1173
Mean 2.41500
Standard dev 0.451835
Max value 6.25000
Min value 1.75000

FSSP LWC (G M-3)

Parameter no. 903
No. of obs 1173
Mean 8.291430e-04
Standard dev 5.177179e-03
Max value 0.103309
Min value 5.583543e-07

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96

Run no. R4

TOTAL WATER CONTENT (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 572
No. of obs 1173
Mean 5.81084
Standard dev 0.120974
Max value 6.28412
Min value 5.57510

DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 529
No. of obs 1173
Mean 278.503
Standard dev 0.285871
Max value 279.433
Min value 277.864

TOTAL WATER DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 725
No. of obs 1173
Mean 278.210
Standard dev 0.293869
Max value 279.331
Min value 277.623

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96

Run no. R4

FSSP MEAN VOL. RAD. (MICRON)

Parameter no. 904
No. of obs 1173
Mean 2.80578
Standard dev 0.759410
Max value 9.72057
Min value 1.75025

FSSP MEAN AREAL RAD. (MICRON)

Parameter no. 905
No. of obs 1173
Mean 2.59874
Standard dev 0.579673
Max value 8.31021
Min value 1.74999

FSSP EFF. RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 906
No. of obs 1173
Mean 3.31179
Standard dev 1.39220
Max value 13.2954
Min value 1.75008

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96

Run no. R4

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 919
No. of obs 1173
Mean 142.130
Standard dev 22.4611
Max value 431.350
Min value 41.0387

PCASP MEAN RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 920
No. of obs 1173
Mean 0.112604
Standard dev 2.467579e-02
Max value 0.371091
Min value 8.928049e-02

PCASP MASS CONTENT (G M-3)

Parameter no. 921
No. of obs 1173
Mean 6.70630
Standard dev 16.9672
Max value 370.493
Min value 0.483111

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96

Run no. R4

PCASP MEAN VOL. RAD. (MICRON)

Parameter no. 922
No. of obs 1173
Mean 0.187651
Standard dev 8.577506e-02
Max value 0.767251
Min value 9.693953e-02

PCASP MEAN AREAL RAD (MICRON)

Parameter no. 923
No. of obs 1173
Mean 0.139415
Standard dev 5.144055e-02
Max value 0.609132
Min value 9.314859e-02

PCASP EFF. RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 924
No. of obs 1173
Mean 0.362870
Standard dev 0.247973
Max value 1.22319
Min value 0.104940

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96

Run no. R5

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

No. of obs 1113
Mean 129.730
Standard dev 160.690
Max value 359.995
Min value 3.018946e-02

WIND SPEED (METRES/S)

No. of obs 1113
Mean 4.08576
Standard dev 1.19694
Max value 7.45005
Min value 1.71757

WIND COMP (METRES/s)

Parameter no. 714,715
No. of obs 1113
Mean north -3.96335
Stan dev north 1.23836
Max north -1.17572
Min north -7.45005
Mean east -3.96335
Stan dev east 1.23836
Max east -1.17572
Min east -7.45005

12:25:30 12:30:08 12:34:46 12:39:24 12:44:02
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96

Run no. R5

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 730
No. of obs 1113
Mean 50.2564
Standard dev 2.753776e-02
Max value 50.3057
Min value 50.2032

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 731
No. of obs 1113
Mean -11.7499
Standard dev 0.145161
Max value -11.4897
Min value -11.9980

CORRECTED NORTH VEL (M S-1)

Parameter no. 735
No. of obs 1113
Mean -1.14793
Standard dev 27.0163
Max value 19.3187
Min value -101.742

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96

Run no. R5

CORRECTED EAST VEL (M S-1)

Parameter no. 736
No. of obs 1113
Mean 25.9949
Standard dev 88.3530
Max value 96.8164
Min value -97.8300

DEICED IND TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 519
No. of obs 1113
Mean 282.311
Standard dev 0.283060
Max value 283.027
Min value 281.448

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 520
No. of obs 1113
Mean 277.956
Standard dev 0.218939
Max value 278.565
Min value 277.386

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96

Run no. R5

NON-DEICED IND TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 524
No. of obs 1113
Mean 282.473
Standard dev 0.236683
Max value 283.056
Min value 281.892

NON-DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 525
No. of obs 1113
Mean 277.986
Standard dev 0.182384
Max value 278.439
Min value 277.582

SURFACE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 537
No. of obs 1113
Mean 283.622
Standard dev 1.51007
Max value 286.229
Min value 279.840

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96

Run no. R5

TOTAL WATER CONTENT (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 572
No. of obs 1113
Mean 5.89874
Standard dev 0.173999
Max value 6.28920
Min value 5.09802

DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 529
No. of obs 1113
Mean 278.542
Standard dev 0.374063
Max value 279.321
Min value 277.095

TOTAL WATER DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 725
No. of obs 1113
Mean 278.191
Standard dev 0.427593
Max value 279.115
Min value 276.127

12:25:30 12:30:08 12:34:46 12:39:24 12:44:02
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96

Run no. R5

J/W LWC (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 535
No. of obs 1113
Mean 0.190675
Standard dev 4.817079e-02
Max value 0.319304
Min value 5.745691e-02

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

Parameter no. 576
No. of obs 1113
Mean 922.538
Standard dev 1.02167
Max value 925.518
Min value 920.933

PITOT-STATIC PRESSUR (MB)

Parameter no. 577
No. of obs 1113
Mean 54.0037
Standard dev 2.21555
Max value 59.1953
Min value 45.5372

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96

Run no. R5

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578
No. of obs 1113
Mean 784.047
Standard dev 9.17220
Max value 798.470
Min value 757.317

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 575
No. of obs 1113
Mean 913.032
Standard dev 9.06862
Max value 927.235
Min value 886.348

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

Parameter no. 574
No. of obs 1113
Mean 0.000000
Standard dev 0.000000
Max value 0.000000
Min value 0.000000

12:25:30 12:30:08 12:34:46 12:39:24 12:44:02
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96

Run no. R5

UPP VIS CLR SIG (W M-2)

Parameter no. 673
No. of obs 1113
Mean 891.840
Standard dev 93.1375
Max value 1140.62
Min value 0.000000

UPP VIS RED SIG (W M-2)

Parameter no. 674
No. of obs 1113
Mean 434.959
Standard dev 51.2532
Max value 568.854
Min value 0.000000

UPP I/R SIGNAL (W M-2)

Parameter no. 675
No. of obs 1113
Mean 457.952
Standard dev 24.8706
Max value 570.606
Min value 373.448

12:25:30 12:30:08 12:34:46 12:39:24 12:44:02
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96

Run no. R5

LWR VIS CLR SIG (WM-2)

Parameter no. 682
No. of obs 1113
Mean 184.842
Standard dev 49.9124
Max value 324.597
Min value 103.226

LWR VIS RED SIG (WM-2)

Parameter no. 683
No. of obs 1113
Mean 96.9093
Standard dev 25.9740
Max value 169.536
Min value 53.4434

LWR I/R SIGNAL (WM-2)

Parameter no. 684
No. of obs 1113
Mean 61.4355
Standard dev 14.6778
Max value 102.760
Min value 35.3087

12:25:30 12:30:08 12:34:46 12:39:24 12:44:02
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96

Run no. R5

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 901
No. of obs 1113
Mean 145.238
Standard dev 45.2669
Max value 256.963
Min value 0.100601

FSSP MEAN RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 902
No. of obs 1113
Mean 5.06449
Standard dev 0.991383
Max value 7.27838
Min value 1.75000

FSSP LWC (G M-3)

Parameter no. 903
No. of obs 1113
Mean 0.118864
Standard dev 6.885020e-02
Max value 0.342055
Min value 5.310489e-06

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96

Run no. R5

FSSP MEAN VOL. RAD. (MICRON)

Parameter no. 904
No. of obs 1113
Mean 5.52668
Standard dev 1.00441
Max value 7.70904
Min value 1.75025

FSSP MEAN AREAL RAD. (MICRON)

Parameter no. 905
No. of obs 1113
Mean 5.29832
Standard dev 1.00564
Max value 7.51060
Min value 1.74999

FSSP EFF. RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 906
No. of obs 1113
Mean 6.01631
Standard dev 1.01612
Max value 8.11891
Min value 1.75008

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96

Run no. R5

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 919
No. of obs 1113
Mean 147.526
Standard dev 68.7854
Max value 443.415
Min value 25.0171

PCASP MEAN RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 920
No. of obs 1113
Mean 0.344832
Standard dev 9.549425e-02
Max value 0.561702
Min value 9.460798e-02

PCASP MASS CONTENT (G M-3)

Parameter no. 921
No. of obs 1113
Mean 212.056
Standard dev 150.872
Max value 848.208
Min value 0.477557

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96

Run no. R5

PCASP MEAN VOL. RAD. (MICRON)

Parameter no. 922
No. of obs 1113
Mean 0.662285
Standard dev 0.141577
Max value 0.880623
Min value 0.104290

PCASP MEAN AREAL RAD (MICRON)

Parameter no. 923
No. of obs 1113
Mean 0.524896
Standard dev 0.129188
Max value 0.758647
Min value 0.100506

PCASP EFF. RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 924
No. of obs 1113
Mean 1.06395
Standard dev 0.177028
Max value 1.23146
Min value 0.111317

12:25:30 12:30:08 12:34:46 12:39:24 12:44:02

TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96

Run no. R6

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

No. of obs 1089
Mean 289.899
Standard dev 108.521
Max value 359.966
Min value 5.776979e-02

WIND SPEED (METRES/S)

No. of obs 1089
Mean 2.23914
Standard dev 1.13923
Max value 4.58581
Min value 9.222022e-02

WIND COMP (METRES/s)

Parameter no. 714,715
No. of obs 1089
Mean north -1.99198
Stan dev north 1.17920
Max north 9.682655e-02
Min north -4.58499
Mean east -1.99198
Stan dev east 1.17920
Max east 9.682655e-02
Min east -4.58499

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96

Run no. R6

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 730
No. of obs 1089
Mean 50.1564
Standard dev 2.439452e-02
Max value 50.2003
Min value 50.1105

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 731
No. of obs 1089
Mean -11.7212
Standard dev 0.151827
Max value -11.4491
Min value -11.9895

CORRECTED NORTH VEL (M S-1)

Parameter no. 735
No. of obs 1089
Mean -9.16354
Standard dev 26.5585
Max value 20.0914
Min value -100.455

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96

Run no. R6

CORRECTED EAST VEL (M S-1)

Parameter no. 736
No. of obs 1089
Mean -22.6398
Standard dev 91.9130
Max value 99.6460
Min value -100.672

DEICED IND TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 519
No. of obs 1089
Mean 287.175
Standard dev 0.238320
Max value 287.674
Min value 286.600

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 520
No. of obs 1089
Mean 282.560
Standard dev 0.167278
Max value 282.931
Min value 281.958

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96

Run no. R6

NON-DEICED IND TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 524
No. of obs 1089
Mean 287.080
Standard dev 0.242143
Max value 287.582
Min value 286.492

NON-DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 525
No. of obs 1089
Mean 282.328
Standard dev 0.169255
Max value 282.696
Min value 281.737

SURFACE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 537
No. of obs 1089
Mean 280.820
Standard dev 2.56280
Max value 286.168
Min value 277.269

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96

Run no. R6

TOTAL WATER CONTENT (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 572
No. of obs 1089
Mean 2.83568
Standard dev 0.144947
Max value 3.15009
Min value 2.10448

DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 529
No. of obs 1089
Mean 268.270
Standard dev 0.634935
Max value 271.835
Min value 266.410

TOTAL WATER DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 725
No. of obs 1089
Mean 267.852
Standard dev 0.700999
Max value 269.249
Min value 264.007

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96

Run no. R6

J/W LWC (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 535
No. of obs 1089
Mean 8.647311e-02
Standard dev 1.681818e-02
Max value 0.124752
Min value 1.098520e-02

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

Parameter no. 576
No. of obs 1089
Mean 905.367
Standard dev 1.08655
Max value 908.395
Min value 902.731

PITOT-STATIC PRESSUR (MB)

Parameter no. 577
No. of obs 1089
Mean 55.3134
Standard dev 1.87544
Max value 59.0802
Min value 50.8654

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96

Run no. R6

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578
No. of obs 1089
Mean 939.433
Standard dev 9.90833
Max value 963.496
Min value 911.856

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 575
No. of obs 1089
Mean 1067.63
Standard dev 9.68024
Max value 1091.53
Min value 1040.98

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

Parameter no. 574
No. of obs 1089
Mean 0.000000
Standard dev 0.000000
Max value 0.000000
Min value 0.000000

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96

Run no. R6

UPP VIS CLR SIG (W M-2)

Parameter no. 673
No. of obs 1089
Mean 1018.64
Standard dev 61.7194
Max value 1181.58
Min value 748.677

UPP VIS RED SIG (W M-2)

Parameter no. 674
No. of obs 1089
Mean 502.747
Standard dev 32.6758
Max value 585.650
Min value 325.754

UPP I/R SIGNAL (W M-2)

Parameter no. 675
No. of obs 1089
Mean 479.384
Standard dev 14.3590
Max value 508.548
Min value 428.916

12:45:53 12:50:25 12:54:57 12:59:29 13:04:01
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96

Run no. R6

LWR VIS CLR SIG (WM-2)

Parameter no. 682
No. of obs 1089
Mean 274.702
Standard dev 100.865
Max value 521.774
Min value 104.839

LWR VIS RED SIG (WM-2)

Parameter no. 683
No. of obs 1089
Mean 135.929
Standard dev 51.5782
Max value 257.500
Min value 44.2378

LWR I/R SIGNAL (WM-2)

Parameter no. 684
No. of obs 1089
Mean 90.2440
Standard dev 27.8529
Max value 159.254
Min value 39.9353

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96

Run no. R6

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 901
No. of obs 1089
Mean 0.000000
Standard dev 0.000000
Max value 0.000000
Min value 0.000000

FSSP MEAN RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 902
No. of obs 1089
Mean 0.000000
Standard dev 0.000000
Max value 0.000000
Min value 0.000000

FSSP LWC (G M-3)

Parameter no. 903
No. of obs 1089
Mean 0.000000
Standard dev 0.000000
Max value 0.000000
Min value 0.000000

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96

Run no. R6

FSSP MEAN VOL. RAD. (MICRON)

Parameter no. 904
No. of obs 1089
Mean 0.000000
Standard dev 0.000000
Max value 0.000000
Min value 0.000000

FSSP MEAN AREAL RAD. (MICRON)

Parameter no. 905
No. of obs 1089
Mean 0.000000
Standard dev 0.000000
Max value 0.000000
Min value 0.000000

FSSP EFF. RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 906
No. of obs 1089
Mean 0.000000
Standard dev 0.000000
Max value 0.000000
Min value 0.000000

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96

Run no. R6

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 919
No. of obs 1089
Mean 115.314
Standard dev 31.7812
Max value 235.666
Min value 55.0322

PCASP MEAN RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 920
No. of obs 1089
Mean 0.103399
Standard dev 7.897982e-03
Max value 0.130054
Min value 8.233982e-02

PCASP MASS CONTENT (G M-3)

Parameter no. 921
No. of obs 1089
Mean 1.29178
Standard dev 1.52953
Max value 13.4791
Min value 0.190292

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96

Run no. R6

PCASP MEAN VOL. RAD. (MICRON)

Parameter no. 922
No. of obs 1089
Mean 0.129154
Standard dev $3.049772e-02$
Max value 0.315893
Min value $9.165382e-02$

PCASP MEAN AREAL RAD (MICRON)

Parameter no. 923
No. of obs 1089
Mean 0.114229
Standard dev $1.352987e-02$
Max value 0.182011
Min value $8.680737e-02$

PCASP EFF. RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 924
No. of obs 1089
Mean 0.172485
Standard dev 0.108142
Max value 1.01691
Min value 0.102124

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96

Run no. R7

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

No. of obs 1168
Mean 266.598
Standard dev 145.090
Max value 359.996
Min value 1.349647e-02

WIND SPEED (METRES/S)

No. of obs 1168
Mean 3.76935
Standard dev 1.07811
Max value 6.84647
Min value 0.906305

WIND COMP (METRES/s)

Parameter no. 714,715
No. of obs 1168
Mean north -3.65896
Stan dev north 1.05887
Max north -0.678253
Min north -6.80477
Mean east -3.65896
Stan dev east 1.05887
Max east -0.678253
Min east -6.80477

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96

Run no. R7

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 730
No. of obs 1168
Mean 49.8365
Standard dev 5.100300e-02
Max value 49.9018
Min value 49.7680

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 731
No. of obs 1168
Mean -11.4243
Standard dev 0.149411
Max value -11.1629
Min value -11.6747

CORRECTED NORTH VEL (M S-1)

Parameter no. 735
No. of obs 1168
Mean -12.7317
Standard dev 22.6909
Max value 3.53731
Min value -105.184

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96

Run no. R7

CORRECTED EAST VEL (M S-1)

Parameter no. 736
No. of obs 1168
Mean 31.4816
Standard dev 87.5767
Max value 101.232
Min value -97.8405

DEICED IND TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 519
No. of obs 1168
Mean 285.469
Standard dev 0.496221
Max value 286.346
Min value 284.367

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 520
No. of obs 1168
Mean 281.122
Standard dev 0.491857
Max value 281.753
Min value 280.166

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96

Run no. R7

NON-DEICED IND TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 524
No. of obs 1168
Mean 285.368
Standard dev 0.499114
Max value 286.260
Min value 284.266

NON-DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 525
No. of obs 1168
Mean 280.894
Standard dev 0.494088
Max value 281.539
Min value 279.933

SURFACE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 537
No. of obs 1168
Mean 286.604
Standard dev 0.128933
Max value 286.962
Min value 286.241

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96

Run no. R7

J/W LWC (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 535
No. of obs 1168
Mean 0.105080
Standard dev 1.599145e-02
Max value 0.166408
Min value 1.018799e-02

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

Parameter no. 576
No. of obs 1168
Mean 955.768
Standard dev 5.60528
Max value 961.574
Min value 945.822

PITOT-STATIC PRESSUR (MB)

Parameter no. 577
No. of obs 1168
Mean 55.2004
Standard dev 2.31854
Max value 64.2838
Min value 49.9178

13:08:37 13:13:28 13:18:20 13:23:12 13:28:04
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96

Run no. R7

UPP VIS CLR SIG (W M-2)

Parameter no. 673
No. of obs 1168
Mean 708.938
Standard dev 111.104
Max value 1046.46
Min value 445.149

UPP VIS RED SIG (W M-2)

Parameter no. 674
No. of obs 1168
Mean 335.043
Standard dev 60.1439
Max value 545.428
Min value 198.237

UPP I/R SIGNAL (W M-2)

Parameter no. 675
No. of obs 1168
Mean 384.389
Standard dev 43.0135
Max value 532.712
Min value 265.258

13:08:37 13:13:28 13:18:20 13:23:12 13:28:04
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96

Run no. R7

LWR VIS CLR SIG (WM-2)

Parameter no. 682
No. of obs 1168
Mean 93.1714
Standard dev 6.94925
Max value 121.371
Min value 83.8710

LWR VIS RED SIG (WM-2)

Parameter no. 683
No. of obs 1168
Mean 46.4657
Standard dev 3.24874
Max value 60.0918
Min value 41.4250

LWR I/R SIGNAL (WM-2)

Parameter no. 684
No. of obs 1168
Mean 30.1620
Standard dev 3.44613
Max value 42.8574
Min value 25.5683

13:08:37 13:13:28 13:18:20 13:23:12 13:28:04
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96

Run no. R7

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 901
No. of obs 1168
Mean 0.746351
Standard dev 2.48179
Max value 55.5510
Min value 2.389336e-02

FSSP MEAN RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 902
No. of obs 1168
Mean 2.28138
Standard dev 0.397624
Max value 5.50000
Min value 1.75000

FSSP LWC (G M-3)

Parameter no. 903
No. of obs 1168
Mean 1.154634e-04
Standard dev 9.111309e-04
Max value 2.151392e-02
Min value 5.582817e-07

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96

Run no. R7

FSSP MEAN VOL. RAD. (MICRON)

Parameter no. 904
No. of obs 1168
Mean 2.58537
Standard dev 0.660463
Max value 7.45545
Min value 1.75025

FSSP MEAN AREAL RAD. (MICRON)

Parameter no. 905
No. of obs 1168
Mean 2.42646
Standard dev 0.512302
Max value 5.98742
Min value 1.74999

FSSP EFF. RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 906
No. of obs 1168
Mean 2.96093
Standard dev 1.13582
Max value 11.5555
Min value 1.75008

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96

Run no. R7

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 919
No. of obs 1168
Mean 142.024
Standard dev 17.4810
Max value 230.885
Min value 79.0771

PCASP MEAN RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 920
No. of obs 1168
Mean 0.114868
Standard dev 8.510854e-03
Max value 0.209375
Min value 9.673929e-02

PCASP MASS CONTENT (G M-3)

Parameter no. 921
No. of obs 1168
Mean 4.73506
Standard dev 5.16994
Max value 80.1667
Min value 0.499179

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96

Run no. R7

PCASP MEAN VOL. RAD. (MICRON)

Parameter no. 922
No. of obs 1168
Mean 0.181332
Standard dev 5.829603e-02
Max value 0.536165
Min value 0.105314

PCASP MEAN AREAL RAD (MICRON)

Parameter no. 923
No. of obs 1168
Mean 0.137237
Standard dev 2.456443e-02
Max value 0.371350
Min value 0.102245

PCASP EFF. RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 924
No. of obs 1168
Mean 0.337875
Standard dev 0.207355
Max value 1.11722
Min value 0.111679

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96

Run no. R8

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

No. of obs 1077
Mean 77.4114
Standard dev 135.285
Max value 359.995
Min value 3.837203e-02

WIND SPEED (METRES/S)

No. of obs 1077
Mean 4.32653
Standard dev 0.952577
Max value 7.11202
Min value 2.01540

WIND COMP (METRES/s)

Parameter no. 714,715
No. of obs 1077
Mean north -4.22644
Stan dev north 0.989874
Max north -2.00417
Min north -7.00400
Mean east -4.22644
Stan dev east 0.989874
Max east -2.00417
Min east -7.00400

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96

Run no. R8

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 730
No. of obs 1077
Mean 49.3784
Standard dev 2.015133e-02
Max value 49.4229
Min value 49.3472

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 731
No. of obs 1077
Mean -11.2466
Standard dev 0.136969
Max value -11.0109
Min value -11.4924

CORRECTED NORTH VEL (M S-1)

Parameter no. 735
No. of obs 1077
Mean 4.21406
Standard dev 26.3964
Max value 92.1040
Min value -99.1394

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96

Run no. R8

CORRECTED EAST VEL (M S-1)

Parameter no. 736
No. of obs 1077
Mean 25.3141
Standard dev 87.6385
Max value 102.460
Min value -101.644

DEICED IND TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 519
No. of obs 1077
Mean 285.214
Standard dev 0.272058
Max value 286.666
Min value 284.613

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 520
No. of obs 1077
Mean 280.896
Standard dev 0.134514
Max value 281.552
Min value 280.626

13:40:24 13:44:53 13:49:22 13:53:51 13:58:20

TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96

Run no. R8

NON-DEICED IND TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 524
No. of obs 1077
Mean 285.111
Standard dev 0.277922
Max value 286.613
Min value 284.504

NON-DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 525
No. of obs 1077
Mean 280.665
Standard dev 0.135378
Max value 281.340
Min value 280.388

SURFACE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 537
No. of obs 1077
Mean 286.141
Standard dev 0.193268
Max value 286.723
Min value 285.783

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96

Run no. R8

TOTAL WATER CONTENT (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 572
No. of obs 1077
Mean 6.22072
Standard dev 0.135219
Max value 6.66361
Min value 5.96320

DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 529
No. of obs 1077
Mean 279.529
Standard dev 0.208447
Max value 280.066
Min value 279.081

TOTAL WATER DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 725
No. of obs 1077
Mean 279.479
Standard dev 0.311787
Max value 280.476
Min value 278.879

13:40:24 13:44:53 13:49:22 13:53:51 13:58:20
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96

Run no. R8

J/W LWC (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 535
No. of obs 1077
Mean $9.555003e-02$
Standard dev $2.191894e-02$
Max value 0.173196
Min value $2.330973e-02$

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

Parameter no. 576
No. of obs 1077
Mean 956.766
Standard dev 1.19199
Max value 963.245
Min value 951.908

PITOT-STATIC PRESSUR (MB)

Parameter no. 577
No. of obs 1077
Mean 54.9449
Standard dev 2.75004
Max value 66.2393
Min value 47.8624

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96

Run no. R8

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578
No. of obs 1077
Mean 481.166
Standard dev 10.3891
Max value 523.607
Min value 424.818

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 575
No. of obs 1077
Mean 609.559
Standard dev 10.3845
Max value 653.661
Min value 554.788

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

Parameter no. 574
No. of obs 1077
Mean 0.000000
Standard dev 0.000000
Max value 0.000000
Min value 0.000000

13:40:24 13:44:53 13:49:22 13:53:51 13:58:20
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96

Run no. R8

UPP VIS CLR SIG (W M-2)

Parameter no. 673
No. of obs 1077
Mean 842.195
Standard dev 126.132
Max value 1195.74
Min value 521.700

UPP VIS RED SIG (W M-2)

Parameter no. 674
No. of obs 1077
Mean 405.844
Standard dev 66.1645
Max value 602.446
Min value 244.647

UPP I/R SIGNAL (W M-2)

Parameter no. 675
No. of obs 1077
Mean 420.167
Standard dev 36.4448
Max value 532.712
Min value 322.922

13:40:24 13:44:53 13:49:22 13:53:51 13:58:20

TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96

Run no. R8

LWR VIS CLR SIG (WM-2)

Parameter no. 682
No. of obs 1077
Mean 95.1126
Standard dev 8.24863
Max value 138.306
Min value 87.5000

LWR VIS RED SIG (WM-2)

Parameter no. 683
No. of obs 1077
Mean 47.3676
Standard dev 4.35199
Max value 68.7860
Min value 42.4479

LWR I/R SIGNAL (WM-2)

Parameter no. 684
No. of obs 1077
Mean 32.1033
Standard dev 3.79440
Max value 52.5977
Min value 28.7339

13:40:24 13:44:53 13:49:22 13:53:51 13:58:20
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96

Run no. R8

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 901
No. of obs 1077
Mean 0.510250
Standard dev 0.227878
Max value 1.07133
Min value 2.412836e-02

FSSP MEAN RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 902
No. of obs 1077
Mean 2.25875
Standard dev 0.339103
Max value 4.10714
Min value 1.75000

FSSP LWC (G M-3)

Parameter no. 903
No. of obs 1077
Mean 4.297253e-05
Standard dev 4.876109e-05
Max value 9.745422e-04
Min value 5.416816e-07

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96

Run no. R8

FSSP MEAN VOL. RAD. (MICRON)

Parameter no. 904
No. of obs 1077
Mean 2.54151
Standard dev 0.550293
Max value 6.73551
Min value 1.75025

FSSP MEAN AREAL RAD. (MICRON)

Parameter no. 905
No. of obs 1077
Mean 2.39449
Standard dev 0.432700
Max value 5.50220
Min value 1.74999

FSSP EFF. RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 906
No. of obs 1077
Mean 2.88155
Standard dev 0.911056
Max value 10.0898
Min value 1.75008

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96

Run no. R8

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 919
No. of obs 1077
Mean 146.880
Standard dev 18.1382
Max value 211.905
Min value 82.0880

PCASP MEAN RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 920
No. of obs 1077
Mean 0.114703
Standard dev 6.427622e-03
Max value 0.137674
Min value 0.100237

PCASP MASS CONTENT (G M-3)

Parameter no. 921
No. of obs 1077
Mean 3.99782
Standard dev 3.99338
Max value 28.3889
Min value 0.451161

1 second averages

A462 26-JUN-96

Run no. R8

PCASP MEAN VOL. RAD. (MICRON)

Parameter no. 922
No. of obs 1077
Mean 0.170741
Standard dev 5.303900e-02
Max value 0.364296
Min value 0.107771

PCASP MEAN AREAL RAD (MICRON)

Parameter no. 923
No. of obs 1077
Mean 0.133124
Standard dev 2.038594e-02
Max value 0.221230
Min value 0.104762

PCASP EFF. RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 924
No. of obs 1077
Mean 0.301801
Standard dev 0.192975
Max value 1.00402
Min value 0.113994

1 second averages